

CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR IN ONLINE SHOPPING

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INTRODUCTION

The customer always tries to find their comfort when it comes to shopping because when we go out for shopping it creates everything much difficult in terms of time taking process and we waste lots of fuel in our vehicle to go from one place to another so online shopping is a great solution to save our time and money. Nowadays there are so many sites that provide us online shopping with great deals especially on festival seasons we get sales on every product. Online shopping is only successful when it is beneficial in terms of money and other aspects like there should be a genuine policy of exchange of shopped material if there is any defect in the product and if we buy clothes and after checking if the size of the dress is not proper so there should be a fair deal to exchange the product and provide the appropriate product to the customer.

In today's scenario Medicines are also available at online platforms they provide medicines at a cheaper rate and deliver their product on time so that customers don't get panic to get their medicines on time they just need to pay money and will get the best facility without any discomfort. Nowadays everybody is busy with their office work so it is difficult to buy the products from the market and when we go home after so much tiredness we want that someone does this work for us so online shopping has made this dream come true because just by clicking product on mobile we can get them at home in the form of online shopping everything will be at home either we can pay the bills online and we can also choose an option of cash on delivery both are safe but make sure that you are buying products with genuine sites which are reliable enough.

If we want to launch any new online website for customers so it is better to make sure the behavior of the buyers because until we have sufficient data about how to convince the customer to buy an online product is the most important step to do our business successfully.

survey, we can get enough data to study how many customers are strongly agreed ne shopping and how many of them are strongly disagree with this process.

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Nowadays we have seen many companies put their survey features on many online platforms like in the advertisement section of You Tube we have seen many companies put the name of their competitor's name in the survey and ask that what product you have bought recently and from which company these data help the company to understand the actual cause of why their product is not getting good response in the market.

BENEFITS OF ONLINE SHOPPING

The very first advantage of online shopping is that customers can buy the product at their comfort like they can buy it from home or workplace as per their convenience. It can save time and effort for the customer because they don't need to start their vehicle and go to the market on an urgent basis. After all, sometime weather doesn't allow us to go out suppose it's heavy rain outside and you don't want to go but still, there is an emergency to buy some groceries for the home that online shopping is a great option.

Sometimes we don't have a vehicle facility at home like we want to go out but our vehicle is out of order and it's urgent to buy the product so this is the real-time to place an order online and the product will come to your door without any discomfort. In some cases, many women don't know how to drive four-wheelers and suppose they need to buy lots of stuff but they don't know how to drive a vehicle and nobody at home to help them in this case also online shopping can work perfectly.

THE DRAWBACK OF ONLINE SHOPPING

When we do online shopping and get a date of delivery in this duration, we get our product at home but due to improper management, we don't get our products on time so we face problems regarding a delay in delivery of our product.

The biggest disadvantage is that you have got all the products at home but you didn't feel the real shopping experience like buying a product from the market and to roam around when you feel tired just go nearby tea stall and have some tea with your favorite snacks and because you go out and shop so it's obvious that you can take dinner out so it's fun to not only buy useful kinds of stuff but to enjoy outside with your family members it's like an outing with your loved ones or with friend circle it makes your bond strong sometimes we see

attractive items while passing through many shops so it's not on our bucket list but still

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we want to buy it because we know that may be next time we don't get such beautiful stuff again so this is called smart shopping which is not possible while we are buying things online.

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Fig. 1: Consumer behavior during online shopping

While customers buy a product, they usually go through these three factors. Social influences always affect them to buy something it doesn't matter they really need that product or just because their neighbors have that so just to show off sometimes people buy products this is called social influence.

Marketing influence is like when we watch our favorite TV shows and suddenly some advertisements come on the TV screen and when we see them again and again somewhere in the mind that place generate like we should change our refrigerator not because it doesn't function well but just because in the market now the new product is launched and it is very attractive all this happened because you have seen it in advertisement otherwise you don't have any plan to buy it.

Situational Influences also plays very important roles because sometimes some difficult situations arise just for time being like you have gone through any site and your mood becomes high to buy the product just because it looks attractive now your mind is not in a to think about whether your pocket allows this or not it happens when we go to the

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mall and our kids want to take chips, chocolates and many other pieces of stuff which we don't need actually but due to the situation we are bound to do so.

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CONCLUSION

Technology allows us to experience online shopping and it will be continuing for many years because it provides convenience to the customers. Online shopping is doing so well that now a day's people don't like to go to the market and to buy the products from stores. However, in some cases, customers want to buy the product after touching and seeing its quality and after that, they want to buy the product in that case, they have to go to the market to feel the product by using senses. Online shopping provides products full information their colors, features and they are offering exchange policy also which makes their work successful and on the other hand they have started a healthy competition among all the sellers so that customer is now getting more benefit just because of this facility.

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